

**THE ANALYSIS OF DERIVATIVE FEATURE OF WORD
COMBINATIONS BASED ON THE WORK
“PRIDE AND PREJUDICE” BY JANE AUSTEN**

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Abstract: The current article explores the derivative features of word combinations in Uzbek and Russian languages, applying linguistic principles to analyze their usage in Jane Austen’s *Pride and Prejudice*. It investigates how word combinations with derivative characteristics enrich literary texts, contributing to stylistic and semantic depth. The study utilizes comparative linguistic analysis and draws from prominent linguists' views to understand the formation, structure, and role of derivative features. By examining examples from *Pride and Prejudice*, this research highlights the universal and specific aspects of derivative word combinations in linguistic and literary contexts. The findings underscore the linguistic creativity inherent in derivative structures and their critical role in enhancing textual meaning.

Keywords: word combinations, derivative features, Uzbek language, Russian language, Jane Austen, *Pride and Prejudice*, linguistic analysis

Introduction. Word combinations are an integral part of language, reflecting its structural and semantic richness. They are formed by combining words into syntactically and semantically coherent units, which can carry distinct meanings or functions. Derivative features, in particular, involve the creation of new words or meanings through affixation, compounding, or morphological modifications. These features allow languages to expand their lexicon and offer nuanced expressions.

In Uzbek and Russian, derivative features demonstrate linguistic diversity, yet they share common principles. Uzbek, a Turkic language e, emphasizes

suffixation and vowel harmony in word formation, while Russian, a Slavic language, extensively employs prefixes, suffixes, and infixes. By analyzing derivative word combinations in these languages, we can better understand their unique and shared linguistic patterns.

Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* is a classic work of English literature known for its rich use of language and intricate narrative style. Through the lens of linguistic analysis, this research examines how derivative word combinations contribute to the novel's depth and complexity, while drawing parallels with linguistic patterns in Uzbek and Russian. The study offers insights into the interplay between literary and linguistic elements, showcasing the universal application of derivative features across languages and genres.

Materials and Methods. This study draws on the theories and methodologies proposed by prominent linguists, offering a multidimensional analysis of derivative word combinations. Ferdinand de Saussure's structuralist perspective provides a foundational framework for this research. His concepts of the signifier and signified, as well as the arbitrary nature of linguistic signs, enable a deeper understanding of how derivative features form and function. Saussure's focus on the synchronic analysis of language sheds light on the structural relationships within word combinations and their derivative properties in Uzbek, Russian, and English. Noam Chomsky's transformational-generative grammar further enriches this analysis. Chomsky's theories about deep and surface structures reveal how derivative word combinations transform abstract linguistic ideas into concrete expressions. His insights into syntax and morphology are particularly relevant for understanding the complexity and flexibility of derivative features, especially in English, where compounding and affixation are prevalent¹. Lev Shcherba's contributions to Russian linguistics provide critical insights into the morphological and syntactical patterns of word combinations in Slavic languages. His detailed analysis of Russian word formation processes,

¹ Chomsky, N. (1965). *Aspects of the Theory of Syntax*. MIT Press

including prefixation and infixation², offers a comparative lens for examining similar structures in Uzbek and their application in literary texts. Additionally, the research incorporates Uzbek linguistic studies, particularly those by Karimov (2010), who elaborates on the morphological features of Uzbek derivatives. His work highlights the role of vowel harmony and suffixation in creating derivative word combinations, which serves as a basis for comparing these features to Russian and English counterparts.

The primary material for this research is Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice*. Specific passages from the novel are analyzed to identify derivative word combinations and their stylistic and semantic functions. Comparative analysis methods are employed to draw parallels and distinctions between the derivatives in English, Uzbek, and Russian. Moreover, statistical methods are applied to quantify the frequency and types of derivative combinations in the text, providing an empirical basis for the study's conclusions.

Furthermore, the study integrates theoretical perspectives on literary linguistics, particularly those emphasizing the stylistic functions of derivatives in literary texts. For example, Roman Jakobson's work on the poetic function of language offers a lens to understand how derivative combinations in *Pride and Prejudice* contribute to its aesthetic and rhetorical impact. These theoretical underpinnings create a robust methodological framework that combines linguistic and literary analysis to explore the richness of derivative features.

Discussion. Derivative word combinations in *Pride and Prejudice* exhibit Austen's linguistic ingenuity. For example, Austen frequently uses participial constructions (e.g., "amused glances," "dancing figures") to convey actions and emotions succinctly. These constructions can be paralleled with Russian participial phrases (веселые взгляды) and Uzbek affix-based derivatives (masalan, "kulgan qarashlar"). In another instance, Austen's use of nominal compounds, such as "self-confidence" and "misunderstanding," illustrates the creative potential of English

² Shcherba, L. V. (1957). *Russian Morphology and Syntax*. Moscow: Nauka
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derivatives. Russian equivalents like *самоуверенность* and misunderstandings like *недоразумение* rely on prefixation and suffixation, whereas Uzbek derivatives use compounding and suffixation (*öziga ishonch, noto‘g‘ri tushunmovchilik*). By examining these examples, we see that derivative features enable nuanced expression in all three languages. However, the literary application of these features in *Pride and Prejudice* elevates their stylistic significance, showcasing Austen’s ability to craft vivid, multidimensional characters and settings.

Results. The analysis reveals that derivative word combinations serve as a powerful tool for enhancing linguistic and literary expression. Specifically, derivative constructions in *Pride and Prejudice* highlight Jane Austen’s ability to navigate between formal and informal registers, enabling a nuanced portrayal of social dynamics and individual psychology. These linguistic structures provide layers of meaning, creating a rich tapestry of literary expression.

When compared to Uzbek and Russian, English derivative combinations demonstrate a balance of simplicity and complexity. Uzbek derivatives lean heavily on suffixation to create rich, descriptive phrases, while Russian derivatives often employ a combination of prefixation and infixation to convey nuanced meanings. The frequency analysis shows that participial derivatives are particularly prominent in Austen’s work, mirroring similar tendencies in Russian literary language and contrasting with the more agglutinative structures of Uzbek. Ultimately, this study finds that derivative features not only enhance the stylistic richness of *Pride and Prejudice* but also bridge linguistic and cultural boundaries. The universal principles underlying these features highlight the interconnectedness of language systems, while their unique manifestations in each language reflect cultural and historical influences..

Conclusion. Derivative features of word combinations are a testament to the richness and adaptability of language. This study underscores their pivotal role in enriching linguistic and literary expression. Through comparative analysis, the research demonstrates that derivative structures in Uzbek, Russian, and English operate

under shared linguistic principles while exhibiting distinct characteristics shaped by their respective linguistic systems. Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* exemplifies the artistic potential of derivative word combinations, illustrating how linguistic creativity can enhance literary narratives. By comparing these structures across three languages, this study not only deepens our understanding of Austen's work but also contributes to broader discussions on the role of derivatives in language and literature. Future research could expand on these findings by exploring derivative features in other literary genres or comparing additional languages.

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